

PROCESSING AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF PTCR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: This paper reports the processing and electrical properties of a new type of PTCR composite materials, which has been made into electric heating cable and plate used in industrial and domestic area. The additives of carbon black and semiconductive ceramic powders were mixed with the matrix of polyethylene powder or epoxy resin. The SEM micrographs of the composites displayed that CB, SBT and silver powders were randomly distributed in the PE or ER matrix. A conducting model of the composite is proposed and its equivalent parallel-series electric circuit is schematically shown, to explain the mechanism of the PTCR effect of the composite.

KEYWORDS: processing, electrical property, PTCR composite and SEM

INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composite materials not only exhibit PTCR (Positive Temperature Coefficient of Resistivity) effect but also behave perfect flexibility [1,2]. A new type of PTCR composite materials was reported here, which has been made into electric heating cable and plate used in industrial and domestic areas.

The PTCR effect of this kind of composite appears when a volume fraction of conductive additive was so large that the percolation threshold of conduction can take place [3,4], usually about 20 - 50 weight percentage of carbon-black is enough. The resistivity of the composite at room temperature is mostly equal to 10^2 to $10^5 \Omega \cdot m$.

EXPERIMENTAL

As conductive and semiconductive additives, commercial carbon black (CB) powder, silver (S) powder or/and $(Sr_{0.2}Ba_{0.8})(Ti_{0.999}Nb_{0.001})O_3$ ceramic (SBT) powder were mixed into polyethylene (PE) powder or epoxy resin (ER) by roll-milling at 150 ~ 180 °C for 30 minutes. The samples were then pressed by a hydropress at 100 ~ 130 °C for 5 minutes. Ga-In solution electrodes were applied. The samples were irradiated in an electron accelerator, 2 MeV for energy, with different irradiation dose. The resistivity of the samples was measured by a multimeter as a function of temperature with a heating speed of 1 °C/minute. The microstructure of the composite materials was observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cooled down to room temperature at a slow speed, sample 1B exhibited lower resistivity at room temperature (R_r) and behaved stronger PTCR effect than that of sample 1G that was cooled at a high speed (Fig. 1). However, there was little difference between sample 1B1 and 1G1 in which a special reagent was added. Partially substituting the CB powder with SBT powders uncoated and coated with a thin nickel layer, the authors produced samples 1B2 and 1G2. The later showed lower R_r and better PTCR effect; moreover, it took short time to reach a thermostatic temperature.

Fig. 1 Temperature dependence of resistivity of the composites

Fig. 2 Effect of additive content on PTCR curve of the composites

The PTCR effect of the samples was also dependent on the cross-linking degree or crystallinity of the PE matrix (Fig. 2). Sample 2A1 in which about 60 % PE matrix was cross-linked revealed stronger PTCR effect than sample 2A2 in which the PE matrix was free of cross-linking. Though influencing R_r , the CB content did not evidently change the PTCR effect of samples 2A3 and 2A4, in which 30 wt % and 50 wt % CB powders has been mixed with the ER matrix, respectively. Nevertheless, the PTCR effect of sample 2A5, which consisted of 30 wt % CB powder and 10 wt % silver powder in the ER matrix, was obviously weakened by the addition of the silver powder; meanwhile, the sample 2A5 behaved remarkably low resistivity within a wide temperature range. The PTCR effect of the material was influenced by the dose of electron irradiation when its degree of cross-linking was relatively low, as sample A1 (Fig. 3) with a, b, c and d representing irradiation dose of 2.0, 1.5, 1.0 and 0 $\times 10^5$ Gy, respectively.

Fig. 3 Effect of electron irradiation dose on PTCR curve of the composites

The micrographs of the composites displayed that CB, SBT and silver powders were randomly distributed in the PE or ER matrix as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 SEM images of the PTCR composites

CONDUCTING MODEL AND EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT

Based on the experimental results, a conducting model of the sample is proposed (Fig. 5) and a parallel-series equivalent electric circuit is schematically shown in Fig. 6. Since the

Fig.5 A conducting model of the sample Fig.6 A equivalent electric circuit of the sample

composite contained three phases: insulating polymer, semiconductive ceramics and conducting carbon-black, the conduction band of the composite with 0-3 connectivity are thus characterized by three parameters: the barrier height of the insulating polymer, E_i , the barrier height of the semiconductive ceramics, E_s , and the conduction level of the carbon-black, E_c . Therefore, the total resistance of the composite, R_t , results from three kinds of resistance: resistance of the polymer, R_i , resistance of the semiconductive ceramics, R_s , and, resistance of the carbon-black, R_c . The heights and widths of the barriers vary, in fact, at different micro-regions in the composite. The resistivity should be calculated by integration within the whole material to obtain more accurate results.

The temperature dependence of the resistivity can be roughly divided into three segments corresponding to three temperature regions. At room temperature the resistivity of the composite was usually small, which might be due to the relatively close distance between the conductive powders of the carbon-black or the semiconductive ceramics. The powders distributed randomly in the matrix of the polymer act as conducting bridges or network in the insulating polymer matrix. Moreover, the tunnel effect might also take place within a thin enough layer of the polymer at relatively low temperature when an electric field is applied. As the temperature is increased, however, the polymer matrix is expanded faster than that of the additives. The numbers of the conducting paths of the network are decreased, and the resistivity is thus increased sharply. So the PTCR effect appears within this temperature range. At a higher temperature, usually above the glass transition point of the polymer, the polymer matrix begins to melt. The concentration of conduction carriers is increased quickly at high temperature, and thus, the resistivity is decreased.

CONCLUSION

A new type of PTCR composites consisting of conductive carbon-black and semiconductive ceramic powders in the matrix of PE or epoxy resin has been developed, which has been made into electric heating cable and plate used in industrial and domestic areas. The amounts of constituents and the processing parameters have effects on the electric properties of the composite materials.

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